

NUMERICAL SIMULATIONS OF OSCILLATORY THERMAL RESPONSE TESTS

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Abstract

Thermal response tests are the most popular in-situ technique to assess ground thermal conductivity and borehole thermal resistance. Conventional tests with a constant heat injection rate do not allow to infer the ground heat capacity. Oscillatory tests are proposed as a tool to evaluate subsurface thermal diffusivity and estimate the heat capacity. Numerical simulation results showed that the frequency of heat injection and the radius of the U-pipe have a significant influence on the temperature response of such tests. The grout's thermal properties and the borehole heat storage effect are main issues to face in order to evaluate the ground heat capacity. Oscillation periods longer than 12 h can however help to have proper penetration depth and limit the borehole influence.

1. Introduction

Thermal response test (TRT) is the most common field method to estimate the subsurface thermal conductivity and the borehole thermal resistance for ground source heat pump systems. Hot water is circulated within the borehole heat exchanger (BHE) in order to inject 50 to 80 W/m (Kavanaugh 2001; Spitler and Gehlin 2015) during conventional TRTs. Low-power tests (10-25 W/m) can also be conducted with heating cables and demonstrated to provide accurate results (Raymond et al. 2015). Tests are commonly carried out for 48 to 72 h with a constant power. TRTs with step heat injection have also been proposed to determine optimal heat rejection/extraction rates (Kurevija et al. 2018).

This study describes the use of an oscillatory heat source in replacement of a common constant power. The hypothesis is that the thermal response of an oscillatory thermal response test (O-TRT) will be affected by heat storage and will provide more information about subsurface and borehole thermal properties when compared to conventional TRT (Oberdorfer 2014). Oscillatory pumping tests have been proposed in hydrogeology as a practical and effective technique for establishing local-scale spatial variability in hydraulic parameters (Guiltinan and Becker 2015). The phase shift and the amplitude attenuation of the recorded signal are

functions of the transmissivity and storativity of the aquifer. Analogously, the thermal conductivity (TC) and heat capacity (HC) of the subsurface can be estimated by the analysis of a similar test in the heat transport domain.

The present contribution aims at defining the most influencing parameters of O-TRT through a parametric numerical study as a preparatory step before moving to field testing. An optimal heat injection protocol is therefore outlined for conducting experiments with both water circulation and heating cable.

2. Methods and techniques

The numerical simulations were carried out with COMSOL Multiphysics® (COMSOL 2019). A 2-D circular model with diameter of 40 m was built to simulate a single-U pipe borehole heat exchanger (diameter 152 mm). A parametric analysis was conducted to evaluate the influence of 11 parameters on the results, namely the thermal properties of the grout, subsurface and heat carrier fluid; the period, amplitude and duration of the oscillations; the diameter of the borehole and the pipes, and the shank spacing. The time steps were set to 0.1 h and, after a mesh independency analysis, the number of triangular elements was set to 9806, the maximum and minimum size of the elements being 0.3 and 0.008 m.

3. Results and Discussion

The frequency of the oscillation is a crucial parameter defining the target of the test, and has the highest influence of the phase shift between the source (heat injection) and the recorded signal (temperature). The results show that the oscillation frequency has the highest average deviation (13.3 %) from the base-case value among all the parameters considered. The minimum, base-case and maximum periods considered are 0.67, 4 and 30 h, respectively. The radius of the U-pipe follows with 11.1 %. Thermal conductivity (2.5 %) and heat capacity (0.8 %) of the backfilling material have a larger influence than the equivalent subsurface properties with 0.17 % and 0.2 %. In particular, doubling the grout HC will result in a larger signal difference on the phase shift than doubling the subsurface HC (Fig. 1). Therefore, as expected, the heat storage effect of the BHE is the largest

obstacle to the evaluation of the subsurface HC, but a longer oscillation period result in a smaller BHE influence. A similar study by Oberdorfer (2014) show that high-frequency tests have small penetration depths and can highlight anomalous borehole thermal resistance due to flaws of the geothermal grouting. On the other hand, high-period tests (low frequencies) are necessary to increase the penetration depth to more than 10 cm and significantly affect the subsurface.

Fig. 1 Comparison between the phase shift of the temperature signal when doubling the heat capacity of the BHE grout (upper graph) and the subsurface (lower graph).

4. Conclusions

A heat injection protocol with period of 12 h, offset of 35 W/m, amplitude of 15 W/m and duration of 48 h has been chosen to move towards field testing with water circulation. Heating cables O-TRT will have smaller offset (20 W/m) and amplitude (5 W/m); both parameters demonstrated to have no influence on the results. Based on this preliminary study and on the response time of the temperature sensors available for field work (20-seconds accuracy, Fig. 2), the subsurface heat capacity can be estimated with a resolution of 0.5 MJ/m³K, i.e. the 19 % of a base-case 2.6 MJ/m³K. Resolution can be increased with longer periods (15 % at 24 h) or more accurate sensors (16 % with 10-seconds accuracy). The linear component of the temperature recordings will be used to evaluate the thermal conductivity and BHE resistance with the same accuracy of conventional tests.

Fig. 2 Detectable phase shift as a function of the response time of the temperature sensors (periods from 1 to 48 h).

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